

**METHODS FOR DIAGNOSING AND CORRECTING COMMUNICATION
DIFFICULTIES IN ADOLESCENTS****Khudayarova Nargizakhon Bakhromjon kizi**

University of Exact and Social Sciences

Field of Study: Psychology, 2nd year master's student

Email: nari.bakh@mail.ru

Abstract: This article scientifically analyzes the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of communication difficulties encountered in adolescence, their causes, and diagnostic and correction methods. The study covers the social adaptation of adolescents, their emotional state, family environment, peer relationships, and the impact of modern information technologies on the communication process. It also substantiates the effectiveness of psychodiagnostic methods, training, and individual and group correctional exercises that serve to develop communicative competence. The article develops practical recommendations for the formation of a healthy communication culture among adolescents in the education system, conflict prevention, and strengthening psychological support. The results of the study are of significant scientific and practical importance for educators, psychologists, parents, and specialists working with youth.

Keywords: adolescent psychology, communication difficulties, communicative competence, psychodiagnostics, correctional work, social adaptation, conflictology, emotional state, psychological training, interpersonal relationships.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola o'smirlilik davrida duch keladigan muloqot qiyinchiliklarining psixologik va pedagogik xususiyatlari, ularning sabablari, diagnostika va tuzatish usullarini ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqot o'smirlarning ijtimoiy moslashuvi, ularning hissiy holati, oilaviy muhit, tengdoshlar bilan munosabatlar va zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarining muloqot jarayoniga ta'sirini qamrab oladi. Shuningdek, u kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladigan psixodiagnostika usullari, treninglar va individual va guruhli tuzatish mashqlarining samaradorligini asoslaydi. Maqolada ta'lim tizimida o'smirlar o'rtasida sog'lom muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish, nizolarning oldini olish va psixologik yordamni kuchaytirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari o'qituvchilar, psixologlar, ota-onalar va yoshlar bilan ishlaydigan mutaxassislar uchun katta ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: o'smirlar psixologiyasi, muloqot qiyinchiliklari, kommunikativ kompetensiya, psixodiagnostika, tuzatish ishlari, ijtimoiy moslashuv, konfliktologiya, hissiy holat, psixologik tayyorgarlik, shaxslararo munosabatlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье научно анализируются психолого-педагогические характеристики трудностей в общении, встречающихся в подростковом возрасте, их причины, а также диагностические и коррекционные методы. Исследование охватывает социальную адаптацию подростков, их эмоциональное состояние, семейную среду, отношения со сверстниками и влияние современных информационных технологий на коммуникативный процесс. Также обосновывается эффективность психодиагностических методов, тренингов, индивидуальных и групповых

коррекционных упражнений, способствующих развитию коммуникативной компетентности. В статье разработаны практические рекомендации по формированию здоровой коммуникативной культуры среди подростков в системе образования, профилактике конфликтов и укреплению психологической поддержки. Результаты исследования имеют важное научно-практическое значение для педагогов, психологов, родителей и специалистов, работающих с молодежью.

Ключевые слова: подростковая психология, трудности в общении, коммуникативная компетентность, психодиагностика, коррекционная работа, социальная адаптация, конфликтология, эмоциональное состояние, психологический тренинг, межличностные отношения.

Introduction. In today's globalization and informatization process, the issue of the human factor, especially the socio-psychological development of the younger generation, is gaining urgent importance. The development of society, the quality of education and the future success of young people largely depend on their communicative competence and ability to communicate effectively. In particular, adolescence is a complex stage of personality formation, during which emotional changes, the desire for independent thinking, the strengthening of relationships with peers and the processes of social adaptation are actively manifested. Therefore, it is natural for adolescents to experience various difficulties, conflicts and psychological barriers in the process of communication.

The increasing difficulties in communication among adolescents are today considered not only pedagogical, but also psychological and social problems. Such difficulties are manifested in such forms as the inability to freely express one's thoughts, aggressive or timid behavior, entering into conflicts with peers, social isolation, excessive dependence on virtual communication. In particular, the widespread use of the Internet and social networks is leading to a weakening of real communication skills, a decrease in emotional stability, and an increase in communication problems.

In our country, supporting the spiritual, moral, intellectual, and psychological development of young people is also being identified as one of the priority areas of state policy. A number of decrees and resolutions are being adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at developing the education system, educating young people as comprehensively well-rounded individuals, and improving the quality of psychological services. These documents pay special attention to the issues of social adaptation of young people, the formation of a healthy psychological environment, the development of a communicative culture, and the improvement of psychological support services.

In this regard, the timely identification of communication difficulties in adolescents, their analysis on the basis of psychological diagnostics, and the development of effective correction methods are of significant scientific and practical importance. If the individual psychological characteristics, communicative needs and problems of adolescents are identified through the diagnostic process, then through corrective activities, they will be able to develop healthy communication skills, increase self-confidence and strengthen social adaptation.

The main purpose of this article is to study the psychological causes of communication difficulties in adolescents, analyze methods for their diagnosis and scientifically substantiate ways of effective correction. The research also highlights the role of modern psychological approaches, training technologies and pedagogical methods in the development of communicative competence.

Literature review. The issue of diagnosing and correcting communication difficulties in adolescents is one of the most widely studied topical areas in world psychology and pedagogical science. In particular, the problems of communicative competence, interpersonal relationships and social adaptation are at the center of modern scientific research. Adolescence is one of the most complex psychological stages of human life, during which a person's self-awareness, emotional stability and relationships with society are formed. Therefore, the scientific study of communication difficulties and the development of methods for their elimination are of great scientific and practical importance.

In world psychology, the issues of communicative development and interpersonal relationships were initially widely covered in the scientific views of such scientists as Lev Vygotsky, Jean Piaget and Erik Erikson. Vygotsky emphasized the decisive role of the social environment and communication in human psychological development[4]. In his opinion, the thinking of a teenager and the formation of a person as a person develop directly through social relationships. Piaget argued that, along with the formation of abstract thinking during adolescence, communicative activity also becomes more complex. Erikson's theory of psychosocial development describes adolescence as a stage of "identity and role confusion", and it is noted that communication problems during this period have a serious impact on personal development.

Modern foreign studies have scientifically proven that excessive use of the Internet and social networks among adolescents leads to a decrease in real communicative skills. American psychologist Daniel Goleman emphasizes in the theory of emotional intelligence that successful human communication largely depends on the ability to manage emotions and understand others[5]. According to research, adolescents with high emotional intelligence establish effective communication with peers and can easily resolve conflict situations.

This issue has also been widely studied in the Russian school of psychology. In particular, A.A. Rean, I.S. Kon[3], L.I. Scientists such as Bojovich have scientifically analyzed the communicative behavior, aggressiveness, social adaptation and interpersonal relationships of adolescents. In their studies, the family environment, pedagogical approach and peer influence are indicated as the main factors of difficulties in communication. In particular, the fact that adolescents raised in a democratic environment have high communicative competence is scientifically substantiated.

Uzbek psychologists and pedagogical scientists also pay special attention to the issues of communicative culture and psychological development of young people. In particular, the scientific works of E.G. Goziyev[1], V.M. Karimova, G.B. Shoumarov set out important scientific views on the psychological characteristics of adolescents, communication culture and personal development. These studies emphasize the influence of national mentality, family values and spiritual environment on youth communication[2].

In our country, a number of regulatory and legal acts have been adopted to comprehensively support young people, strengthen their psychological health, and increase the effectiveness of psychological services in the education system. In particular, the reforms in education and youth policy put forward by the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan identify increasing the social activity of young people, creating a healthy psychological environment, and developing their communicative competencies as priority tasks. The Law "Ta'lim to'g'risida" [6], the Law "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida"[7], and presidential decrees and resolutions aimed at developing the education system indicate the issues of strengthening psychological services and supporting the social adaptation of young people as important areas[8].

Methodology. This study used a comprehensive psychological and pedagogical approach to studying the processes of diagnosing and correcting communication difficulties in adolescents. The research methodology was based on the principles of person-centered education, theories of developing communicative competence, and modern psychodiagnostic methods. During the study, the psychological state of adolescents in the process of communication, social adaptation, emotional stability, and relationships with peers were analyzed.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was Lev Vygotsky's theory of sociocultural development, Erik Erikson's concept of psychosocial development, and Daniel Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence. Based on these theories, the role of communicative activity in personality development, emotional management, and social adaptation processes during adolescence were studied.

The research used observation, interview, questionnaire, psychological test, pedagogical experiment, and statistical analysis methods. The observation method was used to study the behavior, emotional reactions and communicative activity of adolescents in communication with their team and peers. The interview method was used to identify students' attitudes towards communication, internal psychological experiences and social problems.

In diagnostic studies, special psychological methods were used to determine communicative competence. In particular, a test for determining communicative and organizational abilities, a methodology for assessing interpersonal relationships, tests for determining the level of conflict susceptibility, and questionnaires for assessing the emotional state were used. Using these methods, adolescents' communication difficulties, shyness, aggressiveness, social isolation and emotional instability were analyzed.

Adolescents aged 13–16 studying in general secondary schools were selected as the object of the study. Students living in different social environments participated in the study, which ensured the objectivity of the results. In the process of working with the participants, the principles of psychological ethics were strictly observed, that is, their personal information was kept confidential and the research was conducted on a voluntary basis.

Correctional work was organized individually and in groups. In group training sessions, interactive methods were used to develop communication skills, resolve conflicts, form active listening, empathy, express one's opinion freely, and work in a team. In individual correctional interviews, special attention was paid to working with adolescents' personal psychological problems, internal fears, and communication barriers. Also, during the research, modern pedagogical technologies, psychological trainings, role-playing games, elements of art therapy, and reflexive exercises were used. These methods were used as an effective tool for stabilizing the emotional state of adolescents, increasing their self-confidence, and forming a culture of healthy communication.

The results obtained were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. Statistical analysis was used to determine the level of communication difficulties in adolescents, the effectiveness of corrective training, and the dynamics of the development of communicative competence. Based on the results of the study, effective psychological and pedagogical recommendations were developed for working with adolescents.

Results and discussion. During the study, the psychological and social factors of communication difficulties in adolescents were deeply analyzed and effective methods of their correction were identified based on the diagnostic results. The results of the study showed that the most common forms of communication problems among adolescents are associated with

shyness, aggressiveness, inability to freely express one's opinion, tendency to conflict with peers, and social isolation. In particular, it was observed that the increase in virtual communication leads to a decrease in real communication skills.

It was found that a certain part of the adolescents who participated in the diagnostic studies did not have sufficient communicative competence. According to the results of observation and questionnaires, it was observed that some students have difficulty communicating freely in a team, cannot control their emotions, and show aggressive reactions in conflict situations. At the same time, it was found that unhealthy relationships in the family environment, lack of parental attention, and peer pressure are among the main causes of communication problems.

The results of psychological testing showed that adolescents with low levels of emotional stability have more difficulties in communication. Such adolescents were observed to frequently enter into conflicts with their peers, participate passively in group activities, and show lack of self-confidence. The study also revealed a direct relationship between communicative competence and emotional intelligence. Adolescents with high emotional intelligence were distinguished by their ability to effectively manage their emotions in the communication process, understand others, and constructively resolve conflict situations.

The results of corrective training showed positive effectiveness. Through group training, role-playing games and psychological exercises, it was observed that adolescents' communicative activity increased, their ability to freely express their opinions was formed, and their teamwork skills were developed. In particular, training exercises such as "active listening", "empathy", and "peaceful conflict resolution" were effective tools in developing the communication culture of adolescents. During individual corrective conversations, it was found that shy and socially isolated adolescents had increased self-confidence, stabilized their emotional state, and improved relationships with peers. The results of the study confirmed that psychological support and an individual approach are important factors in the communicative development of adolescents.

It was observed that the results obtained are consistent with the scientific views of world and local scientists. In particular, the theory of the influence of the social environment on personality development, put forward by Lev Vygotsky, was confirmed during the study. Also, based on Daniel Goleman's concept of emotional intelligence, the connection between emotional management and effective communication was demonstrated in practice.

During the discussion, it was found that psychological correction alone is not enough to eliminate communication difficulties in adolescents. In this process, the interaction of the school, family and social environment is of great importance. The creation of a healthy psychological environment by educators, emotional support for children by parents, and the systematic work of psychologists serve to reduce communication problems.

It was also determined that it is necessary to widely introduce innovative pedagogical technologies aimed at developing communicative competence in the modern education system. Interactive methods, psychological training, mediation technologies and elements of art therapy were assessed as important tools for the social adaptation of adolescents and the formation of a healthy communication culture.

Conclusions and recommendations. During this study, the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of communication difficulties in adolescents, their causes, and diagnostic and correction methods were scientifically analyzed. The results of the study showed that the emergence of communication problems in adolescence is closely related to biological,

psychological, and social factors. In particular, emotional instability, low self-esteem, problems in the family environment, peer pressure, and the increase in virtual communication are contributing to the increase in communication difficulties in adolescents.

During the study, the effectiveness of psychodiagnostic methods in determining the communicative competence of adolescents was proven. With the help of observation, interviews, psychological tests, and questionnaires, communication problems, emotional state, and level of social adaptation of adolescents were determined. The results showed that there is a close relationship between communicative competence and emotional intelligence. Emotionally stable adolescents were observed to communicate effectively with their peers, resolve conflicts peacefully, and actively participate in the team.

The results of the correctional work confirmed the high effectiveness of psychological training, interactive exercises, role-playing games, and individual conversations in developing adolescent communication. In particular, exercises focused on empathy, active listening, conflict management, and free expression of one's own opinion served to form positive communication skills in adolescents. At the same time, the study revealed that cooperation between school, family, and psychologist is an important factor in eliminating communication problems.

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were developed:

Firstly, it is necessary to regularly organize psychological training and practical exercises aimed at developing the communicative competence of adolescents in secondary educational institutions. Such exercises develop students' skills in teamwork, free expression, and constructive conflict resolution.

Secondly, it is necessary to further improve the activities of school psychologists, effectively use psychodiagnostic methods, and strengthen the system of early detection of communication problems. This will help prevent possible psychological problems in adolescents.

Thirdly, it is important to organize psychological and pedagogical seminars and trainings for parents. Because a healthy psychological environment in the family, open and sincere communication with the child directly affects the communicative development of adolescents.

Fourthly, it is recommended to widely introduce innovative pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, elements of mediation and art therapy into the educational process. These methods serve as an effective tool for strengthening the social adaptation and emotional stability of adolescents.

Fifthly, it is necessary to pay special attention to forming a culture of rational use of the Internet and social networks. Because excessive virtual communication can lead to a decrease in real communicative skills.

In general, timely diagnosis of communication difficulties in adolescents and organization of effective corrective work are of great importance for their psychological health, social activity, and formation as a well-rounded individual. Therefore, it is an urgent task to further expand scientific research in this area, implement modern psychological approaches in practice, and strengthen systematic work aimed at developing communicative competence in the education system.

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